

Considerations regarding accelerations, penalties, and extensions in the time schedules of major construction contracts.

Abstract - This paper examines the interrelated roles of acceleration, delay penalties, and time extensions in major construction and industrial plant contracts within the evolving framework from Total Cost Management (TCM) toward Systemic Value Management (SVM). Building on classical project scheduling theory (CPM/PERT), it highlights how the cost–time relationship, typically characterized by a minimum at the optimal execution time, underpins both acceleration bonuses and delay penalties. The analysis shows that deviations from the contractual baseline schedule increase total costs asymmetrically, challenging the common contractual assumption that acceleration premiums and delay penalties are equivalent.

The study further explores the structure and application of time penalties, emphasizing the importance of clearly defined key events and the limitations of relying solely on final completion milestones, particularly in large-scale, multi-phase industrial projects. It also addresses contractual practices such as penalty caps and the interaction between time and technical penalties.

A central contribution of the paper is a quantitative model for defining technical penalties based on deviations from guaranteed performance parameters. By linking measurable process flows (e.g., energy, materials, fluids) to their economic impact over the plant lifecycle, the model derives penalty values through discounted cash flow analysis. This approach enables a more rigorous and economically grounded determination of penalties compared to heuristic or precedent-based methods.

The paper concludes by situating these contractual mechanisms within a broader SVM/ESG perspective, arguing that improved analytical rigor, supported by advanced computational tools, is essential for managing increasingly complex, long-term industrial projects.

Keywords: Contractual Penalties; Project Scheduling Optimization; Cost–Time Trade-Off (CPM/PERT); Technical Performance Guarantees; Systemic Value Management (SVM)

1. Introduction

In the discussion in this paper, which falls within the specific topics of acceleration, penalties, and extensions in the time schedules of major construction contracts, the general knowledge required for planning, management, project progress and control methodologies is assumed. Specifically:

- the financial significance of the area under the cost-time curve for comparative estimation of the financial cost of alternative projects or for comparing different possible reconfigurations in the event of a schedule revision;
- scale effects in cost planning;
- the integration, at least graphically, of time and costs into a single progress parameter, since both time and costs are always two external constraints contractually established for the execution of a project or program;
- the use, in the planning or schedule revision phase, of two opposing approaches: "as soon as possible" and "as late as possible," in allocating activities within the time allowed by the schedule, in order to optimize both economic and financial aspects, without, however, excessively criticizing the entire duration of the project or its interconnected elements.

All the aspects to be considered in the systemic risk assessment of a project, program or long-term contract and in any case illustrated in the work taken as reference here [1].

Too often in the practice of Total Cost Management (TCM) and contract management, we have neglected to reflect on the fact that the ability of a project to generate adequate cash flows to repay the investment required and at the same time guarantee a return – for financiers and any legal entities (such as a special purpose vehicle) for the construction, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning at the end of the cycle – although it constitutes a necessary condition, in practice it does not prove to be a sufficient condition to bring the project to its natural state of initiation, management, and conclusion of the production cycle for which the project was born. Upon closer inspection, the success or failure stories of the different types of projects, it seems, rather, reasonable

to conjecture that it is the system of values within which the project is contextualized and carried out that decisively contributes to determining its outcomes. Here, the notion of values takes on the broad meaning of shared norms, behaviours, objectives, and attitudes that are structured and strengthened throughout the social body of a civil society, in contrast to a condition of widespread anomie, if not even conflict between values perceived as opposing [1]. Strategic reflections and works in academia and associations suggest the need for a transition from traditional approaches, of which TCM itself can be considered a consolidated expression, to more integrated and systemic approaches that take into account the general concept of Value in its holistic and semantic, as well as economic, complexity.[2],[3].

The actual transition from TCM to Systemic Value Management (SVM), especially when approached through ESG (Environment, Social, Governance) criteria, is a gradual and lengthy process. It must integrate established procedures and practices with new ones, which must delve into the details of specific individual cases and develop metrics for variables that are not directly measurable in economic terms, but which frequently require the development of highly precise evaluation scales on a case-by-case basis. While the availability of modern AI systems and multivariate computational methods makes the development of such metrics possible (for example, by rediscovering the utility function), highly advanced training is still required for practitioners of managerial disciplines, who must fully understand and master these methods to employ them in the projects, programs, or contracts assigned to them.

The following regarding accelerations, penalties, and extensions was only theoretically a possible common practice a decade ago [4], because in practice, although applicable, it wasn't used then, leaving room for simpler and less demanding methods that were neither efficient nor optimized. Perhaps because the saying "the best is the enemy of the good" holds true in management as well? The case is presented here almost as a possible candidate for an "unsolved case", even if only as a preliminary argument to consider in the SVM and ESG context outlined above, to reflect on a problem that, while necessary to address, doesn't appear easily solved in all its more traditional and well-known aspects. This is especially true because change is considered almost always uncomfortable, demanding, and challenging: it doesn't generate traction and can sometimes lead to errors that expose the proponent to a loss of credibility. Thus, we forget that those who expose themselves and make mistakes are forgivable, but those who don't even try have already condemned themselves.

2. Accelerations and Penalties

There's a fundamental connection between penalties and acceleration bonuses, as both have a direct impact on the contractual timeline. However, to properly understand this connection, it's necessary to consider the tender phase for a given contract.

It is normally assumed (see L. Yu Chuen.Tao – Practical Applications of PERT and CPM – Franco Angeli Editore) that during the tender process: “If we want to accelerate the duration of an activity to reduce the duration of the project, it is clear that this will cause an increase in direct costs and a decrease in indirect costs”. For direct costs, consider, for example, overtime or organizing multiple work shifts, more equipment, etc., to achieve a shorter time; while for indirect costs, consider production losses (e.g. reductions that the increased density of the program entails), higher overheads and any penalties incurred for , a longer than expected time.

Fig. 1 – Optimization of time and costs during the tender phase by the Supplier/Contractor

Then, the various participants (and among them the one who will be the chosen supplier or contractor) formulate their own offer to carry out the work or system requested in the contract in a time t_0 at a price C_0 , which, minus the margins, is the expression of the minimum cost, suitable for a tender situation, that each bidder is able to formulate by organising the necessary resources in an optimal way.

The theory of that particular programming technique, known as CPM (Critical Path Method), in fact, maintains that in every type of project the costs:

- the direct ones C_d : normally decreasing over time; i.e. to pay for labor, work means and equipment, etc.);
- the indirect ones C_i : normally increasing as a function of time - including the general and fixed ones C_f (normally constant, but with a stepwise trend beyond certain limits, e.g. to enhance existing plants to be used);

they are combined in such a way that the trend of the total cost C_t as a function of time is that shown in Figure 1, for which three different possible times are identified:

- *a usual time* t_M : identified by index M , which represents the time required without any planning and control, to which a cost C_M higher than the minimum is associated;
- *a normal time* t_0 : identified by index 0, which represents the time required resulting from careful planning and optimal use of resources, to which the minimum cost C_0 is associated ;
- *an accelerated time* t_m : identified by index m , also called "crash time" or the minimum possible time, for which marginal increases in expenditure for acceleration cannot in any case produce further reductions in time in reality.

It follows that in the tender situation mentioned above, all bidders (therefore also the successful tenderer who will ultimately be the supplier or contractor chosen by the client) will tend to formulate the minimum price associated with t_0 to obtain the contract.

Once the contract is awarded, any deviation from t_0 will result in an increase in cost for the supplier or contractor.

A deviation in the left-hand neighbourhood of t_0 will increase total costs due to the increase in direct costs, while a deviation in the right-hand neighbourhood of t_0 will increase total costs due to the increase in indirect costs, in which the prudent supplier or contractor will have also taken care to include penalties for delays with respect to t_0 and the production losses associated with the delays themselves.

The singularity of the cost function C_t represented in Figure 1, that is, the minimum (in some cases a cusp) corresponding to t_0 , sometimes "surprises" some representatives of clients who, also by virtue of a "role-play", do not understand why suppliers or contractors, once the contract has been issued, advance claims for costs both in the case where they are asked for an acceleration (movement of t_0 in a left-hand neighbourhood) and in the case where they are asked for a deferral (movement of t_0 in a right-hand neighbourhood).

Ultimately, both penalties for delays and bonuses for accelerations are among the contractual tools that clients reserve the right to make available, during the performance of a contract, to influence the completion times of the works and services contracted or provided.

During the contract closing phase, however, penalties may also take the form of contractually permitted recourse against the client to "recover" any losses, real or presumed, incurred during the contractual relationship due to causes directly attributable to the supplier or contractor.

Although the cost function C_t , represented in Fig. 1, is a sufficient reason for the connection between acceleration bonuses and penalties set in a contract, it is not clear, however, why in some client's organization (and perhaps here it is a matter of custom) it is considered absolutely "rational" to think that in a neighbourhood $\pm\Delta t$ of t_0 , which is not extremely large, the value of a possible acceleration bonus $+\Delta C$ to obtain a program compression equal to $-\Delta t$, can be considered equal to the penalty $-\Delta C$ corresponding to a delay on t_0 equal to $+\Delta t$. This "rationality" is broken, at least in theory, in some cases (e.g. in the presence of a cusp) in which the values of the slope (i.e. the derivatives) to the right and left of the minimum point vary strongly even for small values of the neighbourhood $\pm\Delta t$ (see the trend of curve 1 in red, in figure 1).

This likely stems from a shortcoming in many contracts, which, while providing for and quantifying a penalty for any delays, do not explicitly provide for or quantify a possible acceleration bonus. This is because the latter is a contractual provision—although provided for by the legislation of many clients—but is used extremely sparingly.

Thus, in those few cases in which an acceleration $-\Delta t$ is decided, the quantification of the amount of the premium is usually established, by a sort of "sui generis" analogy, assuming the value of the inverted penalty corresponding to the delay $+\Delta t$ to be valid.

The conclusion of this discussion leads us to say that it is a good idea, during the tender phase, to ask bidders to quantify any acceleration premium, should the client deem it necessary.

Finally, it is worth remembering that penalties are essentially divided into:

- penalties for temporal effects (i.e. linked to whether or not the deadlines set out in the chronological schedule are maintained);
- technical penalties (usually related to failure to maintain guaranteed performance or exceeding pre-established values relating to particular parameters, such as energy, fuel, reagent consumption, etc.).

Time penalties, and to some extent acceleration bonuses, have in common the possibility of being determined using financial criteria, especially in the final stages of a project, quantifying them based on the failure or early production of the plant/work or service being built. However, in these cases, it should be remembered that contractual penalties are subject, under the Civil Code, to legal constraints, which stipulate that the cumulation of time penalties (i.e., for delays) and technical penalties (i.e., for failure to achieve guaranteed performance) cannot exceed 20% of the total contractual compensation.

For this reason, it is often found that many contracts establish temporary penalties that can reach a maximum of 10% of the total contractual compensation, while the other 10% is reserved for technical penalties.

Fig.2 – Linearization of Time/Cost relation

Returning – in Fig. 2 – to the three times and costs mentioned at the beginning, that is:

- **usual time** t_M associated with a cost C_M higher than the minimum;
- **normal time** t_0 associated with a minimum cost C_0 ;
- **accelerated time** t_m associated with a cost C_m higher than the minimum;

and assuming that at t_0 we are dealing with neighbourhoods of the direct and indirect cost curves in Figure 1 that can be approximated by straight lines, we have Figure 3 from which we can deduce that the ratio:

$$\phi = (C_m - C_0) / (t_0 - t_m) \quad (1)$$

It is useful to identify, in a program with many activities, which of these are most convenient to accelerate.

The CPM theory mentioned above tells us, in fact, that “The optimal project acceleration criterion consists in choosing, in order to reduce the implementation time, those activities that present the lowest increase in direct cost per unit of time” (see L. Yu Chuen.Tao – Practical applications of PERT and CPM – Franco Angeli Editore), that is, precisely those with the lowest ϕ (marginal cost of crashing (€/time unit)).

3. Time Penalties

Time penalties are typically included in a contract and apply in the event of a delay in meeting certain contractual deadlines set for a key event.

The choice of the key event to be subjected to a penalty is, in principle, not very generalizable (unless using the same acceleration method with the reversed sign), nevertheless it should always follow the following criteria:

- the penalized key event must always be unequivocal, precisely identifiable in concrete terms, and well defined within the scope of the contract;
- Responsibility for the failure to achieve the key event within the established timeframe (based on the contractual provisions), and therefore for any delays, must be attributable solely to the supplier or contractor (for example, through events such as: shipment of materials, preparation for testing, preparation for start-up, etc.), even if these delays may obviously have contributed significantly or simply as contributory causes, reasons not attributable to the supplier or contractor themselves (for example, strikes, natural disasters, late project approval by the client, scrap castings or forgings for large machines, unforeseen environmental processing difficulties, use of advanced technologies that have not been fully tested, etc.);
- in the case of work divided into games, each game should have its own penalized key event, distinct from key events in other games;
- in the case of logically sequential events for the purposes of the construction of the work or plant (for example, one cannot begin if the other has not been completed), a single key event must not be identified on the last event from a chronological point of view for the purposes of the penalty;
- where complex contracts involve a single lot of very different phases such as design, material procurement, manufacturing, and on-site construction, penalizing the on-site construction phase is not always sufficiently precautionary. However, progressively increasing penalties for key final events corresponding to each different phase can be a more effective tool for keeping a pulse on the situation than any other " *off-line* " tool for monitoring the progress of the work.

Some of the above criteria, however, have not always been widely accepted in the current contracts of various public and private clients.

For example, in the past, reference was made to Article 29 of the Ministry of Public Works' General Contract Specifications for Public Works, for the case of public works contracting entities. This clearly stated that the penalty is applied based on the completion date of the works and not on intermediate "key events," similar to what occurs in the general specifications of other public bodies.

The practice of identifying only the completion date as the key event subject to penalties likely stems from a principle of maximum contractor independence and minimal interference with the work itself by the client, who can only present himself at the final deadline to demand an account of the delays. The client, on the other hand, should be able to monitor the onset of such delays using " *offline* " systems (thus without interfering with the contractor's activities throughout the entire duration of the work).

This approach may be appropriate for small and medium-sized contracts, where the economic values and financial implications are, overall, relatively limited. However, the current trend among industry and clients, partly to streamline the operational implementation of budget allocations, is gradually shifting toward mega-contracts. These contracts encompass vastly different types of works, jobs, and

systems, sometimes with a significant impact on supplies that, by their nature, require procurement and prefabrication at far from modest factories or workshops.

Offline monitoring of on-site and off-site activities by the client is a fairly widespread and well-established practice, including through expediting procedures *designed* to ensure that all design, procurement, prefabrication, testing, and transportation activities preceding the on-site construction phases are carried out in a timely manner consistent with the construction schedule. The expeditor (person in charge of *expediting* activities) often identifies schedule slippages requiring "recovery" action, well before delays affect the contract deadlines. From that point on, such recovery actions are highlighted at appropriate levels within the client's organization and can even be officially reported to the supplier or contractor in more or less "threatening" terms. However, these actions are certainly ineffective unless appropriate provisions, such as penalties on intermediate schedule deadlines, are included in the contract to prevent expediting (or the *expeditor*) from becoming a blunt weapon in the client's hands.

Indeed, to be effective, any expediting action must be decisive, and to be effective, it must unfortunately rely on the ultimate possibility of "imposing a penalty." Without this, every reminder from the client who has identified delays in the work process could become mere formality, filling a historical archive that ultimately justifies, when the delays have actually occurred and are no longer recoverable, the application of a "final penalty," that is, upon completion of the work.

On the other hand, it's worth emphasizing that experiences in various sectors have shown that "*offline*" progress monitoring worked well (not only in the sense that it disclosed data, but also made it possible to recover from delays by promptly implementing corrective actions when the first signs of delay began to emerge) only in those cases where a connection was established between the progress monitoring system and the accounting system. In other words, the system only worked when it ceased to be "*offline*."

Many managers within client organizations, and even many suppliers or contractors, maintain that the business interest lies in completing work within the deadlines established by the contractual schedule, even attempting to anticipate them. This is not only to avoid penalties, but also because the shorter the schedule itself, the higher the invoicing rate and therefore the profit rate for the same amount of work completed. This general criterion, expressed in this way, is certainly valid, but it contains less obvious implications that undermine its general validity. It must be remembered that every supplier or contractor is, in turn, a client with respect to its "subcontractors" and, like all clients, has a natural interest in following the scheduling policy discussed in section IV.2, known as maximum extension. This means that to maintain high profitability, especially in contracts with a high supply content and payments based on actual revenue, every supplier or contractor has a substantial interest in not committing in advance to expenditures for work, installations, or services that are not necessary to continue immediately accountable portions of the overall project. In other words, it is not worthwhile to spend capital "today" to immediately realize what can be accounted for "tomorrow"; that is, accountable after a contractually established future deadline. This type of disbursement policy is necessary to keep one's financial exposure as low as possible and to maximize the opportunity to earn "currency" (interest) on payments collected and disbursements not made. But this is only a partial aspect of the entire problem, because for the same reasons just mentioned, there is also the tendency of every supplier or contractor, in the absence of specific penalizing constraints on carefully chosen intermediate construction phases, to favor those processes for works, systems, or services that offer the highest profitability, postponing those with the lowest profitability to the final phase of the overall program.

A key role in the supplier or contractor's "strategies" for increasing the financial profitability of the contract can sometimes be played by the interfaces that the client must provide for the implementation of the contract's scope.

These interfaces are all the more relevant in number and importance the larger the work or system to be built and the more fragmented the client is.

Thus, for example, the client issues a contract for civil works, a contract for mechanical works, and a contract for electrical and automation works for a given project, taking on the responsibility of coordinating the project and therefore ensuring the correct interface between the overall project schedule and the schedules outlined in the contracts of individual suppliers or contractors. Thus, the contractor for the mechanical contract, who supplies the systems, cannot begin work unless certain civil works required by him, carried out by another supplier or contractor under the client's coordination, have already been completed. Therefore, the civil works become interfaces for the mechanical works, and any delays in completion of the mechanical works result in delays in the mechanical works, without any penalty for delay being attributable to the contractor for the mechanical contract itself (see diagram in Figure 3). Meanwhile, delays in the civil works have a significant impact on the completion of the project and the start-up of the work or system, resulting in significant costs for the client.

Referring to the proposed scheme, if the delay in completing the civil works for Phase 2 is attributable to the contractor, it is obvious that the penalty should be commensurate with the costs that such delay entails for the client.

Fig. 3 – Effect of program extensions for delays

Since, on the other hand, the mechanical works contractor was already on site for the construction of Phase 1, he would have been able to notice well in advance the delay that was occurring in preparing the civil works for Phase 2. In this way, he will certainly have "allocated" the purchases of materials, components, systems, and services intended for the works planned for that phase at the latest, if the revision conditions conveniently allow it and if there are no contractual obligations for off-site preparation of the mechanical systems to be supplied (e.g., preparation in the workshop) regardless of the preparation of the Phase 2 civil works necessary for the mechanical systems.

Moreover, the delay in such civil works is usually a reason for the mechanical contractor to extend its phase 2 contractual terms, for all purposes (i.e. for the purposes of price revision and penalty).

From the framework outlined above, therefore, it can be deduced that, contrary to appearances, the generic principle stated, according to which a contractor has an interest in completing his work as early as possible, must be scaled down according to each specific case, also taking into account what was said in the previous paragraph (Figure 1) regarding the trend of the total cost of a project once it has been scheduled.

In reality, once the planning has been completed and a certain cost has been set, which is ultimately what allowed the contract to be won in a regular tender, the supplier or contractor's interest lies in "maintaining" the contractual schedule. If anything, more generally, it can be said that the supplier or contractor's interest is to increase the area under the diagram of the client's disbursements to itself (shift or deformation to the left) and reduce the area under the diagram of its own disbursements to its "subcontractors" (shift or deformation to the right) so that the difference between the two areas is as large as possible, representing an indicator of the contract's financial profitability.

4. Force Majeure and Extensions

To clarify and take into account the possibility of delays in the interfaces mentioned above, a specific case worthy of mention is certainly constituted by supply contracts for work, for which some contracting authorities provide separately a portion of the price, the payment terms and a schedule for the supply itself and the same amount for the assembly and on-site work.

For these contracts, it is common to start the supply schedule from the date of signing the contract or a certain number of months after that date (this event is called *the initial reference date*), while for the on-site work portion, the start of the schedule is tied to the client's delivery of the necessary interface works. Thus, any delay in the delivery of the interfaces automatically realigns the chronological schedule in all respects, through a rigid shift in the durations, or rather, the contractually established periods for the on-site work (unless a judge orders it!). This allows for a certain flexibility in contractual management, thus avoiding the need to amend the contract every time there is a delay in the delivery of the interface works.

However, another "uniqueness" that can sometimes be encountered in supply-to-work contracts is the presence of multiple penalties for multiple key events. In fact, in the case of contracts of a certain significance, in addition to the usual penalty for the completion deadline, a penalty may also be applied to the deadline for initial commissioning or the assembly deadline. The three deadlines differ from each other because:

- the assembly term identifies the moment in which the assembly and construction activities on site have been concluded with the sole performance of the tests foreseen during such works such as: non-destructive tests and controls, hydraulic or pneumatic tests, checks of correct execution according to specified technologies, compliance with the executive regulations of the contract;
- the deadline for readiness for initial start-up identifies the moment in which all on-site construction activities have been concluded, following the successful completion of the so-called "blank tests" (circuit tests, planimetric and altimetric checks and machinery alignment, simulated functional tests of individual subsystems);
- the completion deadline instead identifies the moment in which the supply, following the successful completion of the functional and acceptance tests, enters into operation; the client thus has the right to provisionally accept the supply, with the right to use it and, once the warranty period has elapsed without inconvenience, to accept the supply definitively.

The contractual inclusion of a penalty for any delays in these three different deadlines serves different purposes in each case, as they refer to substantially different situations. In the first case, the penalty on the assembly deadline aims to avoid delays in the on-site construction phase, which is one of the most costly and often restricts the start of construction activities elsewhere, but is not necessarily associated with a high investment value for the client. In the second case, the penalty on the on-site preparation deadline aims to avoid delays in the tests leading to the commissioning of the system, which, although overall less costly than the construction activities, occur chronologically after them and therefore involve a higher investment value at the time the tests are conducted. Finally, in the third case, the penalty on the completion deadline aims to avoid delays in the commercial commissioning of the plant, delays that, if they were to occur, would lead to net losses due to lost production precisely when the investment is at its maximum.

From this, it's clear that the penalty for any delays in each key event cannot be the same, but is logically tied to the burden the delay creates. Nonetheless, in current practice, it's common to find that, in individual contracts, the first two objectives are combined into a single penalty for the initial commissioning deadline. Equally often, when this occurs, the penalty for the completion deadline is omitted, partly because in complex projects, the start of operational testing depends on the availability of multiple systems, acquired under different contracts, which are rarely all available at the same time for the start of testing on the completed project as a whole.

5. Technical Penalties and a model for their definition when preparing a contract

In the preparation of many important contracts, where the prior quantification of technical penalties for any deviations that may actually occur from guaranteed parameters of the work or finished system can be extremely important, too often a superficial and approximate approach has been observed. Sometimes, even a failure to identify the correct parameters to be subject to the guarantee, and therefore to technical penalties, has been observed, to avoid considering procedures perceived as unusual "alchemies" on which contractual sanctions can be imposed.

Fig. 4 - When the penalty is completely unavoidable there remains a single hope: "Someone up there loves us, may be! "

The times we live in, however, require careful management of contracts, thus forcing companies that have never considered adequately addressing this issue in their relationships with suppliers or contractors to abandon past traditions. It may seem strange, but one of the strongest arguments from certain corporate bodies, especially technical ones, against an innovative solution to contract drafting and management problems seems to be this: "If it's never been done, there must be a reason!" Thus, in a society that has literally "shredded" the old values of the past, the value of tradition resurfaces in these circumstances, supporting a sort of indolence towards innovation.

In essence, in the past, some contracting bodies or organizations have sometimes deemed it preferable to use a convenient "express termination clause" in the contract, in accordance with Article 1456 of the (Italian) Civil Code, rather than "waste time" studying contractual mechanisms, due to technical penalties, of whose validity and effectiveness the entire organizational structure was not truly extremely convinced.

The aforementioned Article 1456 of the Civil Code states verbatim:

"The parties may expressly agree that the contract will terminate if a specific obligation is not fulfilled in the manner established. In this case, termination occurs automatically when the interested party declares to the other that it intends to avail itself of the termination clause."

Thus, it is usually stated in the written agreement between the client and the supplier or contractor that if the contractual object does not meet the requirements set out in the client's technical specifications (or other annexes to the contract prepared by the latter), the client retains the right to reject the work or system and proceed with the termination of the contract.

In this way, it seems that many people responsible for designing, preparing, and managing a contract feel sufficiently protected against a possible poor outcome of the work or system.

To cast doubt on the vagueness and limited practical utility of the contractual clause that we so often rely on with reckless ease, we should also carefully consider the following articles of the (Italian) Civil Code regarding the termination of the contract for breach:

"Art. 1453 - Termination of contract for breach. In contracts with reciprocal performance, when one of the contracting parties fails to fulfill his obligations, the other may, at his discretion, request either performance or termination of the contract, without prejudice, in any case, to compensation for damages.

Termination may be requested even when the lawsuit was initiated to obtain performance; however, performance can no longer be requested once termination has been requested. From the date of the termination request, the defaulting party can no longer fulfill his obligation.

"Art. 1455 - Significance of non-performance. The contract cannot be terminated if the non-performance by one of the parties is of little importance, taking into account the interests of the other."

"Art. 1458 - Termination of a contract for breach has retroactive effect between the parties, except in the case of contracts with continuous or periodic performance, in which case the effect of termination does not extend to performance already performed. Termination, even if expressly agreed upon, does not affect the rights acquired by third parties, without prejudice to the effects of the transcription of the request for termination."

"Art. 1460 - In contracts with reciprocal obligations, each party may refuse to fulfill his obligation if the other fails to fulfill or does not offer to fulfill his, unless different terms for fulfillment have been established by the parties or result from the nature of the contract. However, performance may not be refused if, having regard to the circumstances, such refusal is contrary to good faith."

From a careful reflection on these articles it should be clear that every termination clause expressed in the contract is automatically connected to regulatory provisions regarding:

- compensation for damages and rights acquired by third parties;
- the lawfulness of a breach by one of the parties involved, if there are also breaches by the other party (as there always are!);
- the need to assess the significance of the breach;
- the irreversibility of the procedure for terminating a contract once requested.

This makes express termination clauses in contracts "the last resort" for serious breaches of contract, and which, in any case, once undertaken, would not be so much clear proof as the final act of failure of a project and the contract it originated.

Fig. 5 -On-site assembly of a steam turbine and its auxiliaries, components on which a "technical penalty" usually applies for failure to comply with "guaranteed performance"

In practice, the reality is that a supplier or contractor rarely presents the client with a finished work or system with deficiencies so serious as to render the work or system itself unusable. Rather, there are specific cases where deviations from the actual technical parameters established in the contract, while imposing a greater burden on the client over time (for start-up, operation, or production), and allowing for less efficient performance and efficiency, still allow the work or system to be used for its intended purposes. In these specific cases, the disproportion and inadequacy of the express termination clause is evident, and it is equally clear that it would be appropriate to have "mechanisms" (rather than "alchemies," as some have disparagingly called them) in the contract to compensate, at least partially, the client for the increased cost incurred compared to the expectations inherent in the contract.

Fig. 6 - Main transformer of a "component" power plant par excellence subjected to technical penalties for "losses"

This certainly doesn't mean that the express termination clause should be banned, which is sacrosanct, not only for highly uncertain contracts or those involving highly innovative projects. Instead, it is essential that, when drafting a contract, we always, and to the greatest extent possible, attempt to identify key technical parameters that can be used to develop a more operational and certainly more effective contractual safeguard. This is necessary to achieve one of the key objectives of any project, one that is too often overlooked: quality. Indeed, quality can be achieved not only through technical monitoring plans throughout the entire process of completing a contract, but (if I may use the expression!) by "waiting" for the supplier or contractor, measuring them on the degree to which they have met the requirements of the work or system, established during the tender process, that are most important to the client.

It should not be forgotten, however, that the practical survey (through measurement) of parameters relating to those requirements, once the work or plant is finished, often involves a cost that can sometimes even reach a few percent of the total amount of a contract. Therefore, the use of the suggested methodologies must be used "cum grano salis", that is, in any case where "the game is worth the candle".

A first-line and certainly not new methodology for identifying and quantifying the technical penalties to be included in a contract during the tender phase could be to focus on identifying the hourly flows:

$$f_a ; f_b ; f_c ; f_d , \dots f_j ; \dots f_x ;$$

at the supply limits of the contractual "object", which should occur under operating conditions established by the project as "reference conditions".

Fig, 7 – Flows at the interfaces of the contractual "object" on which to calculate values for technical penalties to be introduced in the contract

It will therefore be necessary to focus, for example: on the kg/hour of raw materials required for the process for each hourly production unit; on the cubic meters/hour of fluids required, not only those incorporated into the product, but also those for auxiliary functions (such as refrigeration, heating, etc.); on the kilowatt-hours of energy consumed.

Each of these hourly flows is associated with a unit hourly cost equal to:

$$c_a ; c_b ; c_c ; c_d ; \dots c_j ; \dots c_x ;$$

expressed in €/hour.

Let us now assume that the work or plant covered by the contract, under the operating conditions established in the contract as a reference, functions every day, 365 days a year, with:

- an availability factor **X** (factor referring exclusively to the hours of operation which is obviously less than one - see fig. 2), which takes into account the fact that the work or system will operate with at least some interruptions for maintenance, accidental faults, etc.;
- a utilization factor **K** (obviously also less than one but referring to the potential) which takes into account the fact that it will not operate under the reference conditions set by the project all the time.

Fig.8 - Hours of annual availability for the calculation of X

It will thus be possible to calculate the additional annual cost ΔC , to be compared with the expected cost connected to the expectations established in the contract, if the deviations are known through direct measurement under the reference conditions (detectable only when the system is finished and functioning):

$$\Delta f_a ; \Delta f_b ; \dots \Delta f_e ; \dots ; \Delta f_j ; \dots \Delta f_x ;$$

of the various actual flows from those established in the contract itself. From which:

$$\Delta C = 24 \cdot 365 \cdot X_h \cdot K_p \cdot (\Delta f_a \cdot c_a + \Delta f_b \cdot c_b + \dots + \Delta f_e \cdot c_e + \dots + \Delta f_j \cdot c_j + \dots + \Delta f_x \cdot c_x) \quad (2)$$

where :

ΔC = Annual additional cost from deviations;

8760 = hours/year

X =(availability) and **K**= (utilization)

c_j and f_j → generic state unities

that is to say:

$$\Delta C = 8760 \cdot X \cdot K \cdot (\sum_{j=a}^x \Delta f_j \cdot c_j) \quad (3)$$

If the work or plant has been designed to operate for **n** years, during which it can be assumed that an average annual interest rate on capital equal to **r** will be in force (expressed in centesimal form, i.e. for example 12% $r = 0.12$), the annual increase in costs ΔC that the client will have to face to

operate them could also vary from year to year and increase with the increase in the degree of obsolescence of the work or plant itself.

However, with a certain approximation, it can be assumed that ΔC remains constant if an average value is chosen for the various years, taking into account data obtained from the experience of operation and maintenance, over long periods of time, of similar works, components or systems.

Assuming that ΔC remains constant over the years, or is calculated as an average value taking into account the progression of obsolescence over time, we can calculate what in financial mathematics is defined as: "present value of the final accumulation of n deferred annuities", each with a value equal to ΔC . Taking into account that, according to the rules of financial mathematics, given:

$$q = 1 + r \quad (4)$$

where r is the average annual interest rate defined above, the final present value of an annuity A_n of n constant deferred annuities is

$$A_n = \Delta C \cdot (q^n - 1) / r \quad (5)$$

its current value V_a will instead be equal to:

$$V_a = A_n \cdot (1 / q^n) \quad (6)$$

From this we obtain, by substituting the expression previously found for A_n , which represents the present value of the overall burden to which the client is subject after n years of operation, due to a deviation:

$$\Delta f_a ; \Delta f_b ; \dots \Delta f_e ; \dots ; \Delta f_j ; \dots$$

of the various actual flows from those established in the contract is:

$$V_a = \Delta C \cdot (q^n - 1) / (r \cdot q^n) \quad (7)$$

and substituting the previously found expression for ΔC we have:

$$V_a = 8760 \cdot X \cdot K \cdot (\sum_{j=a}^x \Delta f_j \cdot c_j) \cdot (q^n - 1) / (r \cdot q^n) \quad (8)$$

If V_a instead of being calculated for the set of various flows is calculated for the generic single flow f_j it will be that:

$$V_a = 8760 \cdot X \cdot K \cdot (\Delta f_j \cdot c_j) \cdot (q^n - 1) / (r \cdot q^n) \quad (9)$$

By dividing this value by Δf_j we can obtain the unit penalty p_j to be foreseen in the contract, applicable for each unit of deviation Δf_j , that is the NPV of lifetime cost per unit deviation:

$$p_j = c_j \cdot 8760 \cdot X \cdot K \cdot (q^n - 1) / (r \cdot q^n) \quad (10)$$

freeing itself from the need to know Δf_j already at the stage of drafting the contract, which on the other hand is impossible since Δf_j can only be known on the basis of the work, system or component constructed, following direct measurement during operation under the reference conditions set out in the contract.

The calculation model proposed here in a schematic, general and approximate manner must be appropriately adapted to individual real cases and therefore represents more of a reference example than a generalization of the problem relating to the determination of the contractual elements for the application of technical penalties.

However, it appears to be the backbone of a possible model that can be appropriately set up for a specific situation in which, for each of the n years of operation foreseen in the life cycle of the work or plant, a more precise value of the relevant quantities could be taken into account.

Furthermore, the model can include both inputs and outputs, considering the work or plant covered by the contract as a "system" with its own inputs and outputs (see Fig. 8). This means that the same methodology can be applied to reference design parameters such as fluid flow rates at given temperature and pressure conditions, machinery power supplies and consumption, and production plant capacity, provided that for each unit of deviation, the related unit cost to the client is then determined.

A serious criticism of the model proposed above may arise from the fact that it does not sufficiently take into account the burdens that variations in input or output from the system may cause to the client due to the necessary system modifications resulting from the design. In other words, suppose, for example, that the flow f_j is a fluid flow rate (contractually stipulated among the reference design conditions) at a certain temperature and pressure, necessary to ensure the operation of the work or system. If, once the work or system is completed, or even during the development of the detailed design, this fluid, to ensure operation at the required reference design conditions, must undergo, due to system choices made by the supplier or contractor, a variation Δf_j compared to the contract, this variation will also entail variations in the pumping and transmission system of the fluid itself (flow rates and/or pressures of the pumps, power of the related motors, diameter and/or length of the pipes), with additional burdens for the client that the proposed model does not and cannot account for. In fact, this second, more hidden part of the costs, connected to the plant design variations that a deviation Δf_j of the actual flow from the reference flow generates, depends more than ever on the specific real case and cannot be the object of a generalization except through the introduction of a further multiplicative coefficient H , greater than 1, in the expression that provides p_j .

However, it will be necessary to distinguish at least two different cases:

- a) the contract has as its object a work, a plant or a machine functioning in itself, not inserted into complex works or plants;
- b) the contract has as its object a work, a plant or machinery that does not function in itself, but is inserted into complex works or plants.

In the first case, the proposed model is certainly more valid and the value of H is very close to 1. In the second case, the proposed model is more deficient and the value of H deviates from 1 the more the greater f_j is.

Although this may appear to be a crude approximation that smacks of an expedient rather than a valid technical artifice, it nevertheless has the merit of reminding us that p_j represents, in the proposed form, "a minimum" penalty applicable for failure to perform as guaranteed in the contract, since the penalty for technical causes, established in the proposed manner, does not fully compensate the client for the damage resulting from the failure to fully perform as expected from the commissioned work or system.

In any case, we can be certain that the proposed model, despite the shortcomings described, is certainly more valid than proceeding, as has sometimes been seen done, by taking technical penalty values established in past contracts that are not at all similar and updating them in order to make them valid for new contracts concerning completely different objects.

6. Conclusions

As a good approximation to an "ideal penalty" model, the one presented above could be considered technically sound, economically rigorous, and significantly superior to the norm for contractual practice; however, there is no evidence that it has ever been widely applied in practice. This certainly has not been the case for the approximations it contains, such as:

- It is missing degradation / variability when we assume constant ΔC . In real plants: efficiency degrades; costs vary (energy prices, maintenance); being $\Delta C(t)$ time-dependent.
- It is valid only where (as in the Italian legal framework) $\sum \text{penalties} \leq 20\%$ contract value.
- H may be interpreted as an interface cost multiplier or integration level function of system.
- It must ensure no overlap or risk of double counting (e.g. if penalties include both operational inefficiency AND redesign costs).

Furthermore, the very specific "cold case" example provided herein seems to lead to a series of possible reflections for future developments, reported below.

The types of problems that the transition from TCM to SVM will present are numerous and often unpredictable, especially because they vary from case to case. Their resolution will, however, depend on the preparation and training of managerial disciplines to address them with the help of AI and the growing computational power toward which today's world seems headed. It will be absolutely essential to resolve the problems that arise already during the development and initial planning phase of projects, programs, or construction contracts, especially for large-scale projects scheduled for completion in the medium to long term. An error in timing and costs, but also in environmental, social, or governance parameters, committed during the development or initial planning phase will be difficult to recover during implementation, and cost-overrun and time-overrun cases may increase and become more complex given the introduction of variables that may depend on human factors and are therefore, by definition, unpredictable and possibly subject to errors. The best way to avoid hindering change seems to rest on three different pillars:

- the rapid deployment of AI machine learning on pre-selected cases to accumulate structured historical data series, not only on traditional economic, financial, and temporal variables active in a new SVM/ESG context, but especially on new types of variables, namely those relating to environmental, social, and governance aspects;
- the use of new AI systems and innovative computational power, the necessary training, leveraging multidimensional data analysis techniques [6], and making the results open-access, easily accessible to professionals or practitioners of the required management disciplines;
- the development or rediscovery of tools, methodologies, processes, and techniques suited to the purpose, particularly metrics for variables according to ESG criteria, and the clarification of a possible link between externalities for various pollutants and/or situations of potential environmental damage (e.g., increased depletion of available resources).

But the final questions to be answered, even while fulfilling the three points listed above, remain the same [7] as always: When and under what conditions can the planet's resources become marketable, that is, commodities? Marketable for whom, why, where, when, and how?

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